

SUB-NANOSECOND PHOTONICS

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ABSTRACT

Time-of-Flight (TOF) or LiDAR cameras have to provide centimeter or even millimeter ranging resolution and accuracy for many real world applications. They measure the roundtrip time elapsed between a (short) light flash and the received reflection from an object. The challenges are not only in the task to measure the very short time accurately. They lie also in the fact that the photo receiver input dynamic range has to be extremely high and, especially in automotive applications, the operating temperature range is huge. This paper presents methods, how ESPROS achieves the required performance even with photo detectors with nanosecond response time and the high delay variation over temperature.

KEYWORDS: TOF, LiDAR, ranging, photo detector, imaging, lock-in pixel

INTRODUCTION

Some optical imaging distance ranging principles are based on the speed of light. Such principles are Time-of-Flight (TOF), LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging), or, gated imaging. All these principles use the speed of light and measure basically the elapsed roundtrip time of emitted light from a controlled light source to an object in the scene and then back to the receiver (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Ranging parameters

Since the speed of light is very fast, approx. 300,000 km/s or 300 mm in one nanosecond, sub-nanosecond timing measurement capability is required. Distance measurement resolution of one millimeter needs thus a timing measurement resolution of 6.7 picoseconds.

CHALLENGES

There are four major sources for distance errors to consider: 1) dynamic range, 2) temperature drift, 3) interfering ambient light and/or 4) other light sources. In the following, 1) and 2) only are discussed.

DYNAMIC RANGE

On the photo receiver side, the challenges are extremely high. They should be so sensitive that they allow distance measurement with just a few photons received from an object in the scene. This is the case on the one hand, if the object is far away and does not reflect the light very well. On the other hand, a highly reflecting object close to the ranging device can generate millions of photons which hit the photo receiver in a very short time. The LiDAR equation (1) is a mathematical description of this transfer function:

$$P_R = P_T \cdot \frac{4}{\pi R^2 \theta_T^2} \cdot \eta_{ATM} \cdot \sigma \cdot \frac{1}{4 \pi R^2} \cdot \eta_{ATM} \cdot \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \cdot \eta_{SYS} \quad (1)$$

Whereas P_R is the received optical power (Irradiance), P_T is the emitted optical power, R the distance to the object, θ the emitter divergence, η_{ATM} the atmospheric attenuation, σ the reflectivity of the target, D the receiver lens aperture (diameter) and finally η_{SYS} , the photo detection efficiency of the receiver. Two major contributors are to consider for the dynamic range requirements: The range R and the reflectivity σ . Assuming a range variation from 1 to 100m from the closest to the farthest object, the dynamic variation of the receiver signal is 1 to $100 \cdot 10^6$. In addition to the variation of the range parameter, the reflectivity can vary from 10% (black object) or even less up to several thousand percent in case of a retro-reflector. As a

conclusion, the dynamic range in a typical LiDAR system can vary more than one to one billion or 180 dB. This is impossible to be managed by electronic circuitry. Note that the atmospheric attenuation is negligible.

TEMPERATURE DRIFT

Another challenge is the temperature drift of the rise and fall time in photo receivers. Pixels in CCD or CMOS imagers can have rise times in the nanosecond range. This is fine to measure distance down to sub-centimeter resolution. But their temperature drift is large (up to 10 mm/K), due to the low electron mobility in silicon (Si), which is approx. 1ns/ μm with a bias voltage of 10V. Refer also to Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Electron mobility in float zone Si as a function of temperature (source: www.ioffe.ru/SVA/NSM/Semicond/Si/electric.html, modified by ESPROS)

Especially in automotive applications where the required temperature range is from -40 .. +125°C, the temperature shifts the measured distance in the meter domain. Thus, a precise temperature compensation is mandatory. Luckily, the temperature drift in Si is quite linear in the practically applied temperature range.

METHODS

Dynamic range: In a photo receiver and electronic circuitry, which is used to measure distance by time-of-flight principles, a dynamic range of up to 60-70 dB only is feasible. Thus, other concepts are required to reduce the incoming dynamic range. A parallel separation between the emitter and the receiver light path can reduce the dynamic range dramatically, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Parallel separation reduces the required dynamic range

If the emitter beam and the field of view of the receiver start to overlap at 13 m distance, by using the numerical example above, the required dynamic range is 70 dB only. Thus, a precise optically shaped emitter beam is key for good measurement performance.

Temperature drift:

A precise temperature measurement of the receiver device is mandatory. If the temperature drift of the photo receiver is 10 mm/K, a resolution of approx. 0.1 K is required. In a temperature range from -40 .. +125°, which is 165 K, 11 to 12 bit resolution is desired.

CONCLUSION

Sub-nanosecond photonics to measure range can be achieved with relatively slow electronic devices like LEDs or Si photo diodes. However, control of the "environment" is key to get accurate distance measurements. Firstly, the dynamic range has to be kept as low as possible and secondly, the temperature of the emitter and receiver have to be measured accurately to compensate errors induced by temperature.

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